

Applicability of a handheld NIR spectrometer to determine the quality of maritime pine resin (*Pinus pinaster*) in-situ forest

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Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) tapping was developed through vast areas of the south of France, whose largest forest is in *Landes de Gascogne*, a single-species forest massif with more than 1.3 million hectares of maritime pine (Rosa, Soares, and Tomé, 2018). Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) tapping was at a large scale until 1970. Then, industrial production disappeared due to its low competitiveness at an international level. The objective is to promote tapping in this area by providing to companies a rapid and nondestructive analysis tool to enable them to determine the quality of tinned resin directly in the forest field. Indeed, after a tree is tapped, the collected resin can be distilled in the laboratory into two substances: turpentine, composed of monoterpenes, and rosin, mainly composed of diterpenes, also called resinic acids.

Researches were focused on a miniaturized spectrometer (molecular sensor SCiO™) developed by Consumer Physics. This lightweight spectrometer (about 35 grams) covers a spectral range between 780 and 1110 nm. It allows observation of electronic transitions, harmonics, and combination bands of the molecules present in the resin. The studied qualities include chemical proportion (rate of turpentine) and composition (α -pinene, β -pinene, δ -3-carene, γ -terpinene, dehydroacetic acid, levopimaric acid, abietic acid, neoabietic acid). Parameters were correlated to the spectra in order to build predictive models using partial least squares (Wold, Sjöström, and Eriksson, 2001), independent component analysis (Gustafsson, 2005), and least squares support vector machines (Chauchard et al., 2004) regression methods.

Computed models gave good results regarding almost of all the parameters. Although the study is still underway to try to improve the predictive models, results of this exploratory study are promising and confirming that handheld NIR spectrometer could be a good alternative for screening quality parameters of pine resin directly in the field.

Keywords: quality, analyse in-situ forest, maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) resin, predictive models, NIRs

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